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The Modern Generation of Teachers in the Context of the Educational Organization Life Cycle

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Abstract

Every day new organizations are established. At the same time, every day hundreds of organizations are liquidated forever. Those who know how to adapt are likely to thrive, but the inflexible ones tend to disappear. Some organizations develop faster than others and fulfill their aims better than others. The manager should know at what stage of development the organization is and be able to assess whether the accepted leadership style corresponds to this stage.

That is why there has been accepted the universally known concept of the life cycle of organizations as predictable changes with a certain sequence of states over time. The theoretical basis was the results of research by Russian and international scientists in the field of systems theory, corporate management, organization's life cycle theories and crisis management. Research into the development of the human body performed by Vygotsky and it is also mentioned in the current research. The aim of our study is to put into practice the approaches proposed in modern management to make the preschool organization efficient and effective. The results show that a mutually complementary team will provide the result if the members adhere to different approaches and the tasks of each member are clearly defined.

Key words: change management concept, management, effectiveness, organization efficiency, leader-manager, organization life cycle theory.

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Introduction

To make an insight into any problem (a car breakdown, family disorder, trouble at work) will show that a failure has occurred, and it is caused precisely by the fact that something has changed. What is required for this change?

Adizes (2009) proposed his own theory of management - the concept of managing change and solving problems caused by them. It addresses the issue of management education.

The challenges, which are manifestations of disintegration as a result of change, need to be addressed. However, any decisions that heads of organizations make to meet these challenges give rise to new changes, and therefore new discrepancies leading to new problems. The purpose of any form of organizational leadership is to solve the today's problems and anticipate the tomorrow's ones. And that means change management.

The relevance of this work is due to the need for managers to pay attention to the theoretical foundations of the organization functioning. This is important so that the development methods introduced by executives correspond to the level of natural development of the organization. The use of graphical, visual models in determining the developmental trends of the company, built on the basis of the theory of life cycle, allows to more likely predict the internal changes of the company. In addition, in order to improve the managerial process, the manager needs to monitor aspects of the organization life cycle theory that appear as a result of new research. Researchers noted that the development of organizations is determined by a certain algorithm common to almost all types of organizations. The identification of such an algorithm allows, with a certain degree of probability, to forecast the onset of crisis situations and develop the tools that will most effectively neutralize their negative consequences. This becomes more relevant in a market economy, when market mechanisms are intensified, the destruction of old economic ties is destructed and new relationships with counterparties are built.

Considering the organization as an economic system from the perspective of the stages of its life cycle, it is possible to quite precisely predict the future characteristics of the organization in order to optimize the managerial impact. Nevertheless, the issues of the manifestation of the stages of the life cycle in the conditions of the development of a market economy have been poorly studied. In addition, there are some differences in determining the directions for improving the management of organizations according to the stages of their life cycle. The main problem in this case is the difficulty of combining the approaches developed by world economic thought with the traditions of the traditional Russian research and the difficulties of developing modern economic reality.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of our study is to put into practice the tools proposed in modern management to make the preschool organization efficient and effective in the short and long term.

Literature review

The literature and management sources' review reveals the material, social, and economic points of view (Blanchard, 2009; Lavizina, 1996; Piskoppel, 1994, Ros, 2005). Change creates problems and the greater the speed and scale of change, the larger and more complex the problem. Why are changes causing problems? Because everything in the world

is a system, be it a person or the solar system. Any system by definition consists of subsystems. When changes occur, they do not change synchronously: some transform faster, others slower. This leads to the disintegration of the system.

The main idea of Adizes (2008a) is that there is no an ideal leader, or manager - that is, the one capable of single-handedly fulfilling all the functions necessary for the effectiveness and efficiency of an organization in the short and long term. Talking about what a leader should do (based on the needs of the organization), modern management literature does not take into account that those who are able to fulfill these recommendations do not exist in nature. All books and textbooks that try to make us perfect managers or leaders come from the erroneous idea of the attainability of an ideal.

We all go the wrong way and waste millions on education and training of leaders on the basis of insolvent ideas. Classics of management theory, including Koontz (2010), and Drucker (1971), as well as current management academics Stephen Covey (1992) and Tom Peters (1988), describe managers as if they all use a single leadership style that can be easily taught to everyone. This overlooks the fact that different people have different approaches to organization, planning and control. Successful management is considered as a model, a template.

All works are dedicated to what is supposed to happen. However, in reality there are many different management styles - both successful and erroneous. The number of combinations of strengths and weaknesses of the leader is infinite. A lot of books have been written on this subject, but most authors focus on behavioral models, considering them in a psychological aspect. "I am a psychologist. I am the head of an educational organization. I am not a management specialist. I'm interested in how different people make decisions, exchange information, select staff and create incentives for their activities, and I'm looking for ways that can help them do their work more efficiently for the benefit of the organization". Adizes' theory (2008a) does not rely on psychological theories, interviews, or controlled experiments.

Planning the change process through model building provides an advantage to the organization. Firstly, modeling is a practical answer to questions regarding improving the organization's activities and increasing its competitiveness. Secondly, the head or management of an organization that has implemented one or another methodology will have information that will allow them to independently improve their organization and predict the future.

When our organization faced the choice of a development model, it took us a long time to consider which model we want to focus our attention on though sorting out, comparing, analyzing. And they chose the model of "life cycles" by Adizes (2008b). Because his theory of the organization life cycles is similar to the periodization of human mental development.

Dwelling on the criterion for age-related periodization the Russian researcher Vygotsky (cited in Piskoppel, 1994) considered mental neoplasm characteristic of each stage of development. He distinguished "stable" and "unstable" (critical) periods of development.

- 1) newborn crisis
- 2) infant age
- 3) the one-year crisis
- 4) early childhood

- 5)) the 3-year crisis
- 6) preschool age
- 7) the 7-year crisis
- 8) school age
- 9) the teen-age crisis
- 10) puberty
- 11) the 17-year crisis.

If we compare the theory of development of organizations of different management methodologies on the example of Greiner (1997) and Adizes (2009) you can see some difference in the Table 1.

Table 1.

<p>The completed model Represents 10 stages from <i>Birth</i> to <i>Death</i>. Company may return with a descending branch of development into the stage of <i>Prosperity</i>.</p>	<p>The Incomplete model There can be an infinite number of stages, but the company can no longer return to the past</p>
<p>Adizes calls the optimal point of development as the stage of <i>Prosperity</i></p>	<p>Greiner does not name the optimal development point, but notes that since any stage cannot last more than 15 years, the company cannot remain at any stage permanently</p>

The factor of the state (protectionism policy) should be considered when regarding the growth and development of the organization	State factor not taken into account
all stages of the organization's growth are considered sequentially	The stages of <i>Courtship</i> , <i>Infancy</i> and are combined into one called <i>Creativity</i>

And in this comparison, the classic Adizes' developmental model (2009) is closer and clearer to us.

The main postulates of the Adizes' model (2009) are the following statements:

- there are problems at each stage of the life cycle;
- organization problems are divided into "growth diseases" and "organizational pathologies";
- as a rule, organizations cope with growth diseases on their own;
- treatment of organizational pathologies requires external intervention;
- the transition to a descending branch of development for the organization is not predetermined;
- the main task of the organization is to achieve the dawn and not fall on the downward branch of development.

The advantages of the model of Adizes (2009) include: independence from the industry; non-normative approach; the "Scenario" approach; optional death of the organization.

The disadvantages of the model of Adizes (2009) include: unclear relationship with other areas of management; lack of explicit criteria for the development of the company.

The objective of the successful management is to make the organization effective and efficient in the short and long term.

Methodology

In the process of research, theoretical, diagnostic, empirical, experimental, methods of mathematical statistics and graphical representation of the results were applied. They are:

1. The study of theoretical aspects and the identification of the nature of *Organization Life Cycle*;
2. Determining the stages of the organization's life cycle; four management code functions.
3. The study of different models of organization life cycles;
4. Determining the actions of the leader at different stages of the development of the organization;
5. The study of problems of adapting the theory of the organization's life cycle to the Russian reality;

6. The description of the stages completed by the preschool educational organization *Kindergarten No. 113* of the Soviet district of Kazan to provide recommendations for a successful transition to the next stage.

It is important to point the four functions of management code according to Adizes (2009). He believes that in order to ensure the proper level of management, the organization should perform four functions: (P) producing results – these are the results for which the organization exists and which determine its effectiveness, (A) administering - administration that ensures productivity, (E) entrepreneuring - entrepreneurship through which change management takes place, and (I) integrating - integration, that is, combining the structural elements of the organization to ensure its viability in the long term.

The PAEI is an abbreviation of 4 English words, denoting 4 basic needs of any organization and corresponding to its main activities, the main roles: manufacturer, administrator, entrepreneur, integrator.

The Adizes' methodology (2008b) is aimed at forming the optimal team composition. In particular, it enables the leader to evaluate how effectively the employee performs each of the four main roles.

Thus, *P* stands for *producing results* where the function is production and the role is the producer. For the manufacturer, a clear task, goal, facts, figures are important. Such employees carry out any, even routine work, which has a clear measurable result. They love the clear and predictable rules of the game, arrangements and instructions. A "pure" manufacturer is a workhorse. He/she comes first and leaves last and is always busy. However, he/she is wary of any innovations and changes; he or she is not able to work in a team. She/he is competent in his or her field, when changing regulations, he or she is knocked out of the working rhythm and does not tolerate a state of uncertainty. This person loves to engage in work processes, which are tuned to the result. He/she is not inclined to follow all instructions, and is sometimes ready to deviate from the rules in order to achieve the desired. He/she needs to see the goal in front of them, and the ways to solve the problem they will figure it out on their own. Therefore, he/she needs to know his or her business thoroughly and understand the little things.

A stands for *administering* where the function is administration and the role is the administrator. These people tend to stay away from problems and difficulties. The zone of their comfort is beyond fuss and all that requires an immediate reaction to what is happening. They follow instructions and rules and scrupulously pay attention to detail. Such employees have strong analytical skills. The "pure" administrator is a bureaucrat. They come to the office and leave on schedule. All papers are removed in place. The minuses include pettiness, pickiness, emotional detachment, and action only according to instructions and lack of initiative. His or her functionality is reduced to a strict adherence to the rules, compliance with standards and deadlines. He/she is inclined to control everyone and everything and likes to make lists and instructions. An administrator can give shape to any crazy idea and make it completely achievable. Such a person sees all the risks initially, before becoming a reality. He/she is worried that all matters are brought to an end. They worry if the information is saved.

E stands for *entrepreneuring* where the function is entrepreneurship, the role is the entrepreneur. An entrepreneur is a creative person; showing courage and willingness to act. They have a highly developed need to change the world around them: creating a new one, developing ideas, updating, a common understanding of technologies, assessing opportunities and threats from the surrounding community - this is their "pet-horse". It is important for them to win and at any cost. The entrepreneur in "pure form" is an adventurer. He/she does not have a clear schedule, but many ideas. And this is the

main thing for him. It is impossible to isolate from the team, often missing important details. The hate routine and they do not tolerate small details. It is difficult for such a person to concentrate on one thing and methodically follow to achieve a result. But he/she has no rival in finding a new line of development or come up with a unique product. He/she is not interested in short-term results and interested in only great ideas.

I stands for *integrating* to suggest the function of integration and the role of the integrator. The integrator is able to maintain an atmosphere of mutual trust and respect and is able to listen and hear. They can resolve conflicts and reduce tension. They as sociable and friendly have the ability to empathy. They are always party people, informal leaders in the team. The cons are a quick loss of interest in the case when much of the work remains unfinished, sharply perception of criticism, and proneness to grievances and gossip. He/she creates a team spirit and he or she follows the rules of the corporation and motivates colleagues to work. The integrator can be passive (he or she himself participates in the group) and active (rallies, but he or she remains aloof). In addition, their activities are vertical (aimed at top management), horizontal (in his or her professional circle) and lower (with subordinates).

The four management functions of P, A, E and I are something like a set of “vitamins” all of which are necessary for the organization maintenance in the short and long term. If at least one of them is missing, the organization is threatened with a disease with certain symptoms:

- the production function is unsatisfactorily fulfilled and the main consumers of the services of our organization (parents) are dissatisfied.
- the administration function is poorly executed and the organization suffers unjustified losses.
- the organization does not cope with the function of entrepreneurship; there are no new ideas or they are not in demand.
- the integration function is not implemented and the company begins collapsing.

However, skillfully nourishing the organization with the missing “vitamin”, it is possible to improve its work in the short and long term.

The implementation of each function provides an answer to the corresponding question.

R - What needs to be done?

A - How to do this?

E - When and why should this be done?

I - Who should do this?

If one function is satisfactorily performed, and the other three do not meet even the minimum requirements necessary to complete the task, there is a certain style of mismanagement, the variety of which depends on which functions remain unfulfilled. People who could perform all four functions at once do not exist in nature. A normal person can cope with one or two. Occasionally, there are those who are able to perform three functions. The manager can successfully cope with each of the four functions individually in solving specific problems, but no one can perform all four at the same time

in any situation. If you do not take the wish for reality, it will inevitably be found that each person has a unique combination of advantages and disadvantages. Adizes' approach (2009) is realistic and defines what people can give each other and what they are capable of despite their inherent weaknesses.

The experimental research site of the study is *Kindergarten of No. 113* preschool, based in the Soviet district in the city of Kazan, the Republic of Tatarstan.

Stages of the experiment:

2014 - *Birth* Stage of the organization

2015 - *Infancy* Stage

2017 - *Rapid Growth* Stage

2018 - *Youth* Stage

Having studied the theoretical material of the Adizes' model (2009), we tried to build a development model of *Kindergarten of No. 113* preschool, using the model as an example.

The Birth Stage

At this stage, the organization existed exclusively in the form of *an idea*, which was formed by the founders, the authors of the article. In the process of considering the idea, its refinement to a "ready-made" state, it took on ever more clear-cut outlines. And it was decided to establish *a Kindergarten* with the emphasis placed on the aesthetic and intellectual development of preschool children through a high-quality educational environment.

In 2014, as part of the social program for expanding preschools in the city of Kazan, the city administration issued a decision to construct a kindergarten to house 140 children at 20 "b", Glushko Street.

At the initial stage, the managers may encounter the following problems, presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Natural problems and errors	Abnormal problems and error
Excessive excitement, fear and insecurity	Total absence of fear and low commitment to the idea
Fuzzy tasks and confusing functions	Excessive time to think over details and dragging out the time
Challenges in choosing priorities: changing the world or making money?	Excessive emphasis on making money

At this stage, the leader encountered such expected problems and errors as:

- excessive excitement, fear and insecurity;
- fuzzy tasks and mixing functions.

The *Infancy* stage began since the opening of the preschool in October 29, 2014, with the first preschoolers and employees admitted.

The efficiency was low. The organization only learned to function effectively. And then, the leader was required high attention of and a strong managerial hand included.

The leader, by example, had to show involvement in the work and focus on results, act as the provider of transparency, confidence and sustainability for the staff.

During this period, the efforts of the administrative team, consisting of the head, the senior educator and the supply manager, were focused on creating a quality education, improving work with children and their parents. Employees did their best (sometimes there were not enough educators for normal functioning) in order to compensate for the lack of experience and achieve the required results. The details are set out in Table 3.

Table 3.

The Expected Problems and Errors	The Abnormal Problems and Errors
Problems associated with first experience using the product or service by end customers	Inability of the company to establish feedback with consumers and solve problems with the product
Difficulties with the release of the finished product (violation of the terms of release and difficulties at the stages of development of the finished product)	Continuous postponement of product release due to minor changes
The desire to receive additional cash resources from the sale non-core goods and services	Launching a “raw” product to the market
Lack of management skills and delegation	Excessive control that paralyzes work
Lack of rules and procedures for effective management	Lack of tolerance for errors and the repetition of errors of the same type
Frequent mistakes made by employees and company manager	The head does not listen to feedback and does not go no contact

It was during this period that the regulatory framework of the preschool educational institution was created: the charter, the local acts were developed and licenses for educational and medical activities were obtained. The development education program had been compiled and approved.

According to Adizes (2009) the managers are likely to face the following problems.

The problems encountered by the authors of the article at the *Infancy* stage were related to the first experience in providing additional paid educational services:

- the desire to receive additional non-governmental funds;
- frequent errors by employees and the head of the organization,
- lack of management skills and delegation.

To meet the challenge we introduced a rigid centralized decision-making system because there was no time for decentralization and the search for compromise solutions.

Establishing the organization in the market of educational services, the growing demand for the provision of educational services of the preschool contributed to the transition of the organization to the next stage of its development - the *Rapid Growth* stage.

At the *Rapid Growth* stage, the educational products of the organization began to be popular and had high loyalty, which allowed the organization to strengthen its position and flourish.

This was expressed in the project activity, in which both teachers, preschoolers and their parents took part. The first large project was *Peoples of the Volga Region* implemented in 2014. The main objectives of the project were to create the development of a poly-lingual environment in the preschool, to get acquainted with the republics and cities of the Volga region, with the culture of the Volga Region peoples. The result of the project was a joint holiday named "Sabantuy is Inviting Guests!"

The year 2017 was dedicated to the Year of Ecology in Republic of Tatarstan. The achievement in our preschool was the *Preschoolers Learn the World of Oil!* project. The goal was the building and development of eco-friendly behavior of children that is a complex of personal qualities that provide a responsible, conscious (axiological) attitude to Nature. Within the framework of the project, a meeting was organized with employees of the Kazan branch of the Tatar Geological Prospecting Department of *TatNeft*, a major Russian oil-extracting company. Together with their parents, the preschoolers visited the Geological Museum, at Kazan Federal University, Kazan, Russia. The highly emotional ending of the project made *the Tale of the Journey of Oil Droplets*. A significant result of the project activity was an article published in # 9-10, 2017 of *Preschool Education*, a Russia-wide specialized journal (Sadretdinova, 2017).

The year 2017 was a real breakthrough for us, as we were able to adequately implement another *A Preschool Educational Institution is a Health-care institution...* project. In the summer of 2017, our kindergarten took a first prize in the City-wide Specialized Contest. This result was achieved through intensive work of the entire team to create projects of various centers in the kindergarten.

We tried so that throughout the kindergarten the pupils had an opportunity to find something they enjoy, for example, an interesting lesson. We took into account the age characteristics of children and their cognitive interests. All game manuals are located along the eco-friendly path in our kindergarten. And there are also centers for the development of aesthetic, musical, visual qualities of children.

The year 2018 was also noted by well-coordinated and focused work of the team. We established a museum in the kindergarten. The museum is part of the kindergarten's subject-developing environment aimed at ensuring understanding and interaction of children of different nationalities in the process of cognitive, play, cultural and leisure activities, focused on the priorities of spiritual values, ideas for the development of personality, individuality of the child.

An important feature of the museum is the participation of children, parents and teachers in compiling it. Preschoolers feel their involvement in the museum. They can participate in a discussion of its subjects, bring exhibits from home; children from senior groups conduct excursions for younger children and replenish them with their creative work.

In real museums you cannot touch anything, but in our *Preschool Local Lore Museum* it is not only possible, but also essential. The preschoolers can visit the Preschool Museum every day, change it yourself, rearrange the exhibits, pick them up and examine them. In an ordinary museum, a child is only a passive observer, and here he/ she are the co-founders, creators of the exposition. And not only the preschoolers themselves but also their parents, relatives and friends. The Preschool Museum is the result of communication, joint work of the educators, children and their families. The formal result of this project was the victory in the city-wide competition *The Local Lore Center - 2018* contest.

During this period, the kindergarten became the seminar base as a part of continuing education courses held by Institute of Education Development of the Republic of Tatarstan, city-wide seminars for senior educators and kindergarten managers. He authors achieved prominent results in team projects, shared their experience at Preschool Methodological Associations sessions, international conferences, published articles in specialized education journals, the education staff took prizes in various professional contests.

According to the Adizes' theory (2009), the problems that the manager faces at the *Rapid Growth* stage are the most dangerous for the long-term prospects of the organization and they can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4.

The Expected Problems and Errors	Abnormal problems and errors
Excessive company confidence in success	Outflow of key people of the company
Confusion about priorities, responsibilities and functions	High priority for every task
Sales acquire more important status than profit	Premature focus on profitability
Lack of control over costs, budgeting and cash flow analysis	Lack of delegation and remote management
Low managerial competence of the leader	Arrogance from leadership positions

At the *Rapid Growth* stage, there is the likelihood of the “Founder's Trap” scenario. This term was introduced by Adizes (2009). It means the organization is highly dependent on its leader, who manages all the processes himself/ herself. But, unfortunately, he/she is not able to allocate time for analysis and solving all the problems.

To avoid this situation, the authors organized the work of temporary creative teams in the preschool to implement the project, which was relevant at that time. Building temporary creative teams and appointment of different members of our teaching staff as their leaders allowed us to update the organizational structure, monitor the quality work of internal processes of information exchange and control. Delegation of authority became an especially important skill in the organization. In addition, the promotion of teamwork helped strengthen the corporate spirit and create a cohesive team.

It is noted that if the delegation process is successful, then the leader can gradually proceed to the process of decentralization of management (transfer of responsibility for decision-making). Before that, the organization was not quite mature.

At the stage of the life cycle, called *Youth*, the preschool staff was reborn into the light, but in a slightly different form. We decided to try ourselves in innovation.

One of the decisions of our team was the decision to participate in innovation at different levels, both urban and federal. The orders were signed on an innovative platform on improving the quality of education at *the Institute for the Study of Childhood, Family and Education of the Russian Federation*, under *the Kazan Education Department* on the topic of *Social Intelligence of Preschool Children* and an order on the implementation of office projects in educational institutions of Kazan, participation in the International *Eco-school \ Green Flag* Movement.

As part of our innovative projects, the preschool was engaged in the transformation of the developing environment in the premises of the preschool. Parents and teachers created vertical multifunctional manuals that allowed a change in play tasks and were available for children at any convenient time.

As part of the office project this year, the manager of the organization took a *Coaching Training Course* that helps in solving managerial problems.

Participation in innovative activities allowed not only to improve the quality of educational services provided under the main program, but also to expand the range of additional educational services.

Now children have the opportunity to engage in figure skating on artificial ice. The objectives of this direction are to strengthen the physical health of preschoolers and the popularization of sports.

Classes in vocal art teach children to relax, confidently stay on stage, have a healing effect and promote the development of creative potential of preschool children. In this course, the preschoolers gain awards in various contests.

In our hectic time it is very important to create a favorable emotional atmosphere in the preschool. It is important to teach children how to relieve stress and relax in time and they successfully achieve it in the sensory room.

At the *Youth* stage, the management culture must transform from an absolute monarchy to a constitutional monarchy. In fact, the decentralization of power should occur, since the organization already has employees who are able to take on the

solution of certain issues. And currently, the senior educator and supply manager have become such-like employees in the preschool under study.

If the manager and the staff do not solve the problems that arise at this stage of the organization's development, there is a risk of returning to the previous stage of your development and, as a result, failure. To achieve sustainable development at the *Youth Stage*, an organization must limit the flexibility that was encouraged in the previous stages of development. At this stage, the mission and values of the organization are of high importance.

The staff has something to work on, they are ready for change, and accept their mistakes and correct them. To do this, managers educate their teaching staff through seminars, trainings, coaching sessions within the team on team building, goal setting and more.

They are striving for the *Dawn Stage*, which represents the golden age. This is the stage when the organization occupies an optimal position on the life cycle curve and reaches a certain balance between flexibility and tight control in management. It happens when the organization has clear goals, everyone has clear priorities and all employees consistently, stubbornly and clearly perform their tasks. The organization is aligned with the mission, strategy, structure, information management processes, resource allocation, and reward systems. The organization works smoothly as a single mechanism.

Any leader wants his or her team to be efficient, competitive and harmonious. How to create a team so that its members complement each other, strive for development and not get stuck in a swamp? The simplest and most understandable solution for a manager at any level can be the methodology for selecting personnel according to the methodology of Yitzhak Adizes (2009). Because it describes the four basic types of personality through the prism of human behavior in the work environment.

Results

The authors believe that an interesting finding of the Adizes methodology (2008a) is that along with the strengths, the weaknesses of employees are considered, while other techniques describe only the strengths. Knowing about the weaknesses of employees allows us to predict possible difficulties for employees and think out ways to overcome them.

Why did the authors decide to implement this method?

1. The four roles of PAEI do not have cumbersome and scientific-clinical descriptions that impede perception and cast doubt on the interpretation of the results.
2. In order to understand the method no specialized education is necessary.
3. The principles of PAEI do not contradict and are combined with any other methodologies that we are used to. In addition, the method is universal: it can be used both in the selection of personnel and in training, internal communications, teamwork, and even in personal life.

As it can be seen, there are many advantages of this strategy that made the authors dare to apply it. We invited our staff to take an on-line test. After reviewing the strengths and weaknesses of each of the roles, analyzing the results of testing of the teaching staff, the researchers received the following data:

- Participants with the most pronounced producer function - 40%;
- Administrators - 13%;
- Entrepreneurs - 17%;
- Integrators - 30%.

After passing the test, the teaching staff received the following recommendations:

1) What to do if you are a producer:

- Before you complete a task, consider whether it is really necessary.
- Make a list of tasks that only you can do.
- Consider long-term results.
- Pay attention not only to the result, but also to the process.

2) What to do if you are an administrator:

- Depart from the plan, take risks. In an era of change, this is necessary.
- Do not judge the colleagues for stepping back from the initial plan.
- Consider each specific situation separately. Sometimes, in order to maintain a good relationship, you have to deviate from the plan.

3) What to do if you are an entrepreneur:

- Do not rush to voice each idea.
- Set aside the decision for a day: you eliminate emotions and have time to think things through.
- Let other colleagues speak out.

4) What to do if you are an integrator:

- If you need to resolve the issue, imagine that you are on a desert island. You have no advisers. The decision is yours.

- Do not be afraid of criticism. If someone does not share your point of view, listen them and share.
- Allow an hour to communicate with colleagues, the rest of the time devote to strategic issues.

Discussions

For each group, the authors of the article tried to choose such techniques that would help our teachers develop the ability to act other roles.

A group of producers faced the problems with generating ideas. They were dissatisfied with something new, unconventional. The colleagues and the head worked on *the Wheel of Balance* method, the purpose of which is the method of analysis and life planning as well as *The 100 Wishes* Technique, which helps build tasks in the long run.

The administration function in our team is at the lowest level. Therefore, it was decided to put into operation such a technique from management as the *SCRUM Board*. The purpose of which is that in everyday worries you can leave in sight only those things that you need to focus on without bothering with what is yet to be done or what has already been done. On the board there are 4 columns on which stickers with the name of cases are glued, according to the instructions. As the work progresses, the employee re-sticks the sticker in the next column.

Colleagues who are inclined to the functions of entrepreneurship and integration were offered the *SMART Analysis* technique.

Together we examined how to set a goal, what results we want to achieve, what actions need to be taken to achieve a goal. And, of course, it is important in this technique to determine the timing for achieving the goal.

In *order* to assemble a team of suitable types and learn to work together for the effectiveness of the entire kindergarten, the staff applies one of the effective methods that are the analysis of functions and powers according to “the vitamin complex” of Adizes (2009). The purpose of this technique is that everyone is invited to take on a role to explore the behavior of a given code. Thus, each time taking on different roles, playing as a team, solving different tasks, the colleagues build the functions according to “the vitamin code” (Adizes, 2009).

The desired results can be achieved if functions *P* and *E* are brought to the forefront. The work efficiency can be gained by using functions *A* and *I*.

A mutually complementary team will provide the result if the members adhere to different approaches and the tasks of each member are clearly defined.

Conclusion

The main idea of the methodology is to understand that all people are different and need each other to achieve common goals. There are no perfect team members. The staff must be able to cooperate efficiently with the actual team-members. It is necessary to create conditions under which the employees will be able to reveal their best qualities. The modern leader, no matter what organization he/she manages, is to determine at what developmental stage their organization currently is.

Knowing the organization developmental laws and the problems that may arise when passing through each stage, a leader needs to skillfully assess how much the accepted leadership style corresponds to the current stage requirements.

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